

Intravenous artesunate for the treatment of severe imported malaria: implementation, efficacy and safety in 1391 patients.

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Running title: Artesunate for severe imported malaria

Brief summary: From 2011, artesunate was deployed in France through a specific program streamlined by prepositioning in hospital pharmacies to treat severe imported malaria. Robust clinical benefit was confirmed in 1391 patients, as in several subgroups. Anemia was the commonest adverse event.

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KEY POINTS: Of 1391 patients with imported severe malaria treated with intravenous artesunate 95.9% survived, 91.6% without sequelae, with similarly positive outcome in children, adults over 50, HIV-infected and overweight patients. Post-treatment hemolysis affected more than 50% of patients of European origin.

ABSTRACT

Background: Intravenous artesunate is the WHO-recommended first-line treatment for severe malaria worldwide, but it is still not fully licensed in Europe. Observational studies documenting its safety and efficacy in imported malaria are thus essential.

Methods: We prospectively collected clinical and epidemiological features of 1391 artesunate-treated patients among 110 participant centers during the first seven years (2011-2017) of a national program implemented by the French Drug Agency.

Results: Artesunate became the most frequent treatment for severe malaria in France rising from 9.9% in 2011 to 71.4% in 2017. Mortality was estimated at 4.1%. Treatment failure was recorded in 27 patients but mutations in the *Kelch-13* gene were not observed. Main reported adverse events (AE) were anemia (136 cases), cardiac events (24, including 20 episodes of conduction disorders and/or arrhythmia) and liver enzyme elevation (23). Mortality and AE were similar in the general population and in HIV-infected, overweight or pregnant patients, but the only pregnant woman treated in the first trimester experimented a hemorrhagic miscarriage. The incidence of post-artesunate delayed hemolysis (PADH) was 42.8% when specifically assessed in a 98-patient subgroup but was not associated with fatal outcomes or sequelae. PADH was twice as frequent in patients of European compared to African origin

Conclusion: Artesunate was rapidly deployed and displayed a robust clinical benefit in patients with severe imported malaria, despite a high frequency of mild to moderate PADH. Further explorations in the context of importation should assess outcomes during the first-trimester of pregnancy and collect rare but potentially severe cardiac AE.

INTRODUCTION

Intravenous (IV) artesunate is the WHO-recommended first-line treatment for severe malaria worldwide. Compared with IV quinine, IV artesunate reduces lethality in Asian adults and in African children by 35% and 22.5% respectively.^{1,2} Artesunate was designated as an orphan drug by the European Medicines Agency in 2007 (EU/3/07/430). Artesunate meeting good manufacturing practice (GMP) standards is currently not available in Europe, and it is not approved by drug agencies in most non-endemic countries. It is therefore not available for emergency use except through specific distribution programs.³ In this situation, patients needing artesunate may not have immediate access to it.^{4,5} Artesunate was developed by Guilin Pharmaceuticals. In 2010, their parenteral formulation was prequalified by the WHO. In June 2019, the American Society of Tropical Medicine & Hygiene raised concerns that the public distribution program could delay the provision of artesunate and result in adverse outcomes for patients, and advocated for a fast approval of artesunate in the US.⁶ In May 2020, the US Food and Drug Administration approved GMP IV artesunate manufactured by Amivas (US) LLC, for the treatment of severe imported malaria.

In France, IV artesunate had been recommended by a national experts panel in 2007,⁷ but the distribution of this off-licensed drug was not organized, leaving IV quinine as the only effectively available option. In 2009, an independent panel of academic experts challenged the national drug agency (ANSM) and in May 2011, IV artesunate (ACE Pharmaceuticals BV, The Netherlands) became available in a temporary use approval program for severe imported malaria.³ A specific distribution program compatible with the emergency treatment of severe malaria was implemented through the prepositioning of artesunate at hospital pharmacies throughout France. The ANSM performed a post-hoc validation of the use of artesunate. This specific program implied that clinicians, biologists and pharmacists involved in the use of artesunate would provide treatment-start-up, treatment-end and post-follow-up efficacy and safety data. This enabled the French program to precisely oversee the implementation of this new treatment.

We assessed the outcome of the program for nation-wide artesunate deployment for severe imported malaria, and the efficacy and safety of this treatment in both the general patient population and in specific patient subgroups.

METHODS

Study population

We analyzed a cohort of patients treated with IV artesunate for malaria in France between 25 May 2011 and 31 December 2017. Observations from the first 123 treated patients have been reported previously and were included

in this analysis.⁸ Data were prospectively collected in the Malaria National Reference Center (MNRC) database shared by a network of 110 sites in France. Additional data were prospectively collected from medical charts and specific distribution program forms³ completed by the attending physicians at the beginning and end of treatment and at the end of patient follow up (FigureS1). All patients who received IV artesunate at an MNRC network site during the study period were included. Data were retrieved from the MNRC database (Voozаноо, Epiconcept) on 3 July 2018.

Adverse events (AE) were obtained from the MNRC database and the national pharmacovigilance system as described elsewhere.⁸ Post-marketing surveillance was done by 31 nationally-distributed pharmacovigilance centers. Additional information on safety was retrieved by the expert group from medical charts and direct contact with pharmacists, physicians and biologists in charge of the patients. No assumption on the imputability of artesunate in the AE was made at the time of analysis.

Case definitions

Definitions used for severe/uncomplicated malaria⁷, parasitological failure (PF) and anemia when reported as an AE are provided in TextS1 and S2. Main outcomes of acute malaria were defined as death or survival at day 28, median length of stay (LOS) in the intensive care unit (ICU) and in the hospital. Definitions used for “geographic origin” are provided in TextS2.

Treatment regimens are indicated in TextS2.

Post-artesunate delayed hemolysis (PADH)

PADH was specifically assessed in a 98-patient subgroup, based on hematological and biochemical parameters (hemoglobin, hematocrit, LDH, bilirubin and reticulocytes) before and after treatment (until day-28 post treatment) as described (TextS2).⁸ The PADH-incidence subgroup comprised all cohort patients with complete day-0 to day-28 biological and clinical follow-up and day 0 frozen serum in the MNRC (TableS1). Their laboratory and clinical data were reviewed by experts who confirmed group allocation based on published criteria.^{9,10}

Detection of Kelch 13-propeller domain mutations

We retrieved pre-treatment frozen whole blood samples from the MNRC for patients presenting it and looked for the Kelch 13-propeller domain mutations (TextS2).

Statistical analysis

Outliers and implausible or missing information (MI) were checked. Implausible values were recorded as missing when no other information could be found. Quantitative variables were expressed as medians (interquartile range [IQR]) or means (SD) as appropriate. Qualitative variables were expressed as percentages. Differences among groups were analyzed with the Fisher's exact test for categorical variables, and the Mann-Whitney test for two or the Kruskal-Wallis test for more than two continuous variables. Stata 13 Statistical Software (College Station, TX: StataCorp LP) was used for all analyses. All reported p values are two-sided. The adjusted chi-square test was used to compare the characteristics of the PADH-incidence subgroup and the whole cohort.

Ethical considerations

The study was authorized by the French National Commission for Data Protection and Liberties (CNIL: declaration number 1223103) and approved by the Ethics Committee for Biomedical Research. (TextS2)

RESULTS

Replacement of IV quinine by IV artesunate to treat severe imported malaria in France

During the transition period (2011-2017), the number of severe imported malaria cases declared to the MNRC and the proportion of severe malaria among all reported malaria cases increased from 2011 to 2014 then stabilized between 2014 and 2017 (Figure1A). Severe malaria-specific lethality decreased from 6.2% in 2012 to 3.4% in 2017 (Figure1B).

The proportion of severe malaria patients treated with artesunate rapidly increased between May 2011 and December 2014 from 9.9 to 61.9%, while that of patients treated with IV quinine decreased from 72.5 to 19.2%. A nearly complete transition was thus observed within 3 years. From January 2015 to December 2017, the proportion of artesunate-treated patients continued to slowly increase, reaching 71.4% in 2017 (Figure1C). Interestingly, almost 25% of severe malaria patients were treated with first-line oral therapy, a proportion that remained stable during the study period, but with a marked switch from atovaquone-proguanil to artemisinin-based combinations (Figure1D).

Description of the cohort

During the study period, 1391 malaria patients, of whom 98.5% (n=1370) had severe *P. falciparum* malaria according to French definitions, were treated with IV artesunate. 145 patients (10.4%) met the French but not the WHO 2015 criteria for severe malaria. Children (<15 years) and the seniors (>65 years) accounted for 9.2% and 8.9% of the cohort, respectively. Fifteen pregnant women were treated, including one in the first, six in the second

and six in the third trimesters (MI for two). There were 98 (7.9%) immunocompromised patients, of whom 67 (5.4%) had HIV. 74.6% of the patients lived in non-endemic areas, 56.7% were born in endemic countries and 67.7% declared an African origin (Table1). Patient characteristics were similar to those of severe imported malaria patients reported by the GeoSentinel analysis in 2017.¹¹

Clinical Efficacy

PF occurred in 27 of the 318 cohort patients who had complete parasitological follow-up (i.e. blood smear available at days 3, 7 and 28). Among the PF patients, 13 had slow parasite clearance (>7 days), seven had early resurgence (before day-8), and seven had late resurgence (between day-8 and day-28). One PF patient died from cardiogenic shock and ventricular fibrillation. No PF risk factors were found in univariate analysis (TableS2) and PF risk did not increase during the study period (not shown). Pre-treatment frozen whole blood samples were available for seven of the 27 PF patients. No *k13* non-synonymous mutants were found in the seven tested isolates.

Forty-one patients died during the study period and 970 were recorded as cured; day-28 outcome was missing for 380 patients (27.3%). Overall mortality was 4.1% (41/1011) when considering only patients with explicitly-reported day-28 death or survival data. The majority (80%) of deaths occurred within the first four days after diagnosis (FigureS2). Median hospital and ICU LOS were 6 (4-8) and 2 (1-4) days respectively (Table2). Blood transfusion was reported in 130 patients (9.3%).

Compared to the general population of artesunate-treated patients, mortality was higher in patients with initial parasitemia >10%, patients aged >50 years and patients of European origin, and lower in patients <15-year-old (1.0%) or of African origin. HIV-positive patients had an increase in total LOS but not an increase in mortality. Pregnant women had outcomes similar to the general population (Table3-1). Initial parasitemia was significantly higher in patients of European origin but similar among the other subgroups (TableS3). Of note, no outcome differences were observed between the patients with initial parasitemia <4% and those with initial parasitemia from 4 to 10% (Table3-1). At the end of follow up, sequelae were reported in 48 patients (8.4% of 574 patients with available information, TableS4).

Safety

Information on AE (absence or presence) was available for 568 artesunate-treated patients. A total of 360 AE were reported for 241 patients (42.4%). 76 patients with declared AE had received another antimalarial treatment (including IV Quinine in 45 patients) before artesunate. Death was reported as an AE in nine patients (Figure2 and TableS5).

Hematological AE were reported in 156 cases (43.3%). Anemia and/or hemolysis were reported in 23.9% (136/568) of patients with available AE data, and were significantly more frequent in initial parasitemia >10% and patients of European origin when compared to patients of African origin (Table3-2). No deaths or sequelae were reported related to hematological AE.

Because PADH can be mild and go unnoticed, its incidence is probably underestimated. This remains true even when AE are recorded prospectively, as in this study. We defined a PADH-incidence subgroup to precisely estimate the incidence of this AE in travelers treated with artesunate. The PADH-incidence subgroup was similar to the entire cohort on most population characteristics, clinical presentation, treatment characteristics and main outcomes. Exceptions were place of residence, sex ratio, mortality and initial parasitemia (TableS1). When systematically assessed, the incidence of PADH was much higher (42.8 % of patients, n=42). Furthermore, its higher frequency in patients of European (57.9%) versus African (29.2%) origin was confirmed (p=0.014) (FigureS3).

In pregnant women, one first trimester hemorrhagic miscarriage was reported. No other pregnancy-related complications were noted apart from benign contractions without cervical dilatation. Other AE included digestive (n=56, including 19 nausea and/or vomiting cases and 22 elevated liver enzyme cases), neurological, (n=40), cardiocirculatory (n=24, including six QT prolongation cases, TableS6), renal (n=18, including 15 renal failure cases), metabolic (n=16 including five hypoglycemia cases), cutaneous (n=14) and splenic (n=2) manifestations. Four cases of multi-organ failure were declared as AE (Figure2 and TableS5). Renal failure was more frequently reported when initial parasitemia was >10%. Renal and cardiac events were more frequently reported in patients of European origin. The incidences of hypoglycemia and liver enzyme elevation were similar in the general and subgroup populations (TableS7). No increase in AE incidence was noted in children, or over/underweight, HIV-positive or pregnant patients (Table3-2).

DISCUSSION

Randomized trials in endemic areas have demonstrated the superiority of artesunate over quinine.^{1,2} Artesunate induces rapid parasite clearance,¹² and its activity on young blood stages reduces the sequestration of parasitized RBC in small vessels, a process that triggers many manifestations of severe malaria. These are strong arguments to adopt IV artesunate as the first-line option in severe imported malaria, as recommended by WHO in 2010 and 2015.^{13,14} Yet, its deployment in non-endemic countries has been slow. The absence of randomized trials comparing artesunate to a reference drug in this non-endemic context and doubts regarding safety of non-GMP formulations have favored the *status quo*, i.e., maintaining IV quinine or quinidine as the first-line treatment.

Finally, the delayed availability of artesunate has led many clinicians to keep on using immediately-available quinine, or quinidine, or even oral drugs instead of switching to artesunate.^{4,5}

In this context, observational studies are the only available option to assess the clinical benefit and safety of artesunate in travelers. Our epidemiological and clinical report on the implementation and performance of pre-GMP artesunate in severe malaria is the largest to far performed in a non-malaria-endemic country.

The nation-wide deployment of IV artesunate in France was swift. An initial reluctance from some prescribing physicians did not impact the pace at which artesunate was adopted as the first-line treatment for severe malaria in France. Compared to references, few anti-infectives have shown benefits on all-cause mortality over the last decades, and this was an important argument for artesunate adoption despite the absence of randomized trials in the specific context of imported malaria. Indeed, due to ethical and logistical constraints, such trials are impossible. That constraint had been perpended by national agencies when debating IV artesunate deployment and was furthermore well grasped by the medical community.

The clinical benefit of IV artesunate met or exceeded that of conventional antimalarials used in severe malaria. Patient age, weight, HIV status or pregnancy did not alter that benefit. We observed a mortality rate of 4.1%, close to the 3.9% and 5% rates reported with IV quinine in travelers.^{15,16} When compared to quinine in travelers,^{15,17-20} IV artesunate did not appear to reduce mortality, but the difference in favor of artesunate fell short of statistical significance. Mortality rates for patients treated with quinine is relatively low (5%) in most non-endemic countries, due in part to the availability and quality of intensive care in them.¹⁶ Demonstrating a statistically-significant superiority for artesunate in terms of mortality in this context would require the inclusion of tens of thousands of patients in a randomized trial. Reduced ICU LOS in artesunate compared to quinine-treated patients was demonstrated in the context of importation.^{15,19} The median ICU LOS in our study (2 [1-4]) was consistent with previous data.²¹

No cases of confirmed parasite resistance to artemisinin were reported and resistance-associated *k13* mutations were not found in the isolates tested. This is likely because very few of the patients in our cohort returned from areas where parasite resistance to artemisinin is prevalent.

The safety of artesunate in travelers was good in observational studies, despite a high incidence of delayed hemolytic episodes (PADH).²¹ Here, we confirmed those observations. Reported AE were estimated as potentially drug-related by physicians in charge, but due to the observational design of our study, causality of artesunate in their occurrence cannot be definitively established. Anemia and/or hemolysis were by far the most frequently-reported AE (37.6% of all). Among those, typical PADH episodes were reported in 32 patients (5.6% of patients

with reported AE). However, PADH is underestimated because it generally occurs after discharge and thus may go unnoticed or unreported. We confirmed that in our specific assessment of incidence in the PADH-incidence subgroup, where a thorough workup was performed. There, typical PADH occurred in 42.8% of patients, confirming the high frequency of these episodes. As stated by WHO in 2013, PADH does not undermine artesunate's superiority over quinine.²² However, the observation of severe cases,^{21,23} although relatively rare, warrants a systematic assessment of the risk of PADH in IV artesunate. The development of a predictive dipstick test performed two to four days after treatment initiation has simplified this assessment.¹⁰ We confirmed here that PADH is more frequent in hyperparasitemic patients and showed that its incidence is twice higher in patients of European origin. This observation conforms with what is known about the main PADH mechanism (synchronous hemolysis of pitted cells as a trigger of the phenomenon)⁹ and with the observation that artemisinin-induced pitting rates are lower in immune vs. non-immune patients.²⁴

Neurological manifestations, elevated liver enzymes and nausea and/or vomiting were also frequently reported, as mentioned by the manufacturer (SPC Guillin) and by previous reports.²¹ Although considered uncommon,²⁵ we observed cardiovascular manifestations in 24 patients, including 20 episodes of conduction disorders and/or arrhythmia. The causal role of artesunate cannot be definitely established in those episodes, as severe malaria itself and preexisting conditions or concomitant medication (including IV quinine) can all be associated with cardiovascular events. Two cases of sinus bradycardia and two episodes of QT prolongation occurred in the absence of shock in patients with no cardiovascular history and who did not receive quinine. The incidence of cardiac AE was lower than those previously reported with IV quinine or quinidine.²⁵ Nevertheless, the possibility of rare artemisinin-mediated cardiac effects should not be ruled out at this stage. Other artemisinin derivatives (artemether, arteether) have been associated with QT prolongation in animal studies,²⁶ but to date, no significant effect has been shown in humans.^{25,27} Electrocardiography should be performed before and during treatment, particularly in patients with preexisting cardiovascular disease, and proactive reporting of cardiac AE should be implemented.

In our study, information was collected by a task force of public sector entities with limited, predominantly academic, specific funding. Thus, our proportion of missing data may be higher than that of conventional prospective trials and a degree of minor AE underreporting is likely. However, the density of the MNRC network, the involvement of the national pharmacovigilance system and the cross-referencing of information sources make it unlikely that a major event went unnoticed.

In conclusion, artesunate can be rapidly implemented on a nation-wide scale. Distribution was streamlined by prepositioning artesunate in hospital pharmacies. The simpler use of artesunate compared to quinine, the lower incidence of AE, including hypoglycemia (<1% in our cohort), and the high cure rates in clinical trials in endemic areas and observational cohorts in travelers.^{8,17–20,28,29} supported its swift, country-wide adoption. We confirmed its robust clinical benefit in a cohort of 1391 malaria patients and in several clinically important subgroups. Taken together, our results advocate for the use of IV artesunate as the first-line treatment for severe imported malaria, as per WHO recommendations. Hematological events—for which a simple dipstick-based predictive process exists—were by far the most frequent AE, but not associated with fatal outcomes or sequelae. Clinicians and patients should be aware of the high frequency of PADH following treatment, particularly in patient of European origin. Similar implementation experiences are ongoing and could be envisioned in other countries affected by severe imported malaria.

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CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

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AUTHORS' CONTRIBUTIONS: C.R., S.J. and P.B. designed and performed research, contributed vital analytical tools, performed statistical analyses, analyzed data, and wrote the paper; P.A.N., E.K., S.L., B.H. and B.L.V performed research, contributed to data collection and analysis, and wrote the paper; M.T. and R.P. designed research, analyzed data, and wrote the paper; A.T., O.M., C.C., H.D. and D.C. performed research and contributed

to data collection. F.G., J.Y.S., F.B., S.H., N.A., A.A., O.B, M.D. and E.C. performed research and wrote the paper.

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	N (% of available data)
Geographic origin (n=1224)	
African	829 (67.7)
European	362 (29.6)
Asian	11 (0.9)
Other	22 (1.8)
Location of birth (n=1174)	
Endemic area	666 (56.7)
Non-endemic area	508 (43.3)
Location of residence* (n=1056)	
Endemic area	268 (25.4)
Non-endemic area	788 (74.6)
Immunodepression (n=1240)	
Yes	98 (7.9)
HIV	67 (5.4)
Cancer	10 (0.8)
Corticosteroid therapy	6 (0.5)
Hematological malignancy	5 (0.4)
Organ transplant	3 (0.2)
Other	5 (0.4)
Unknown	2 (0.2)
Pregnancy (n=1293)	
Yes	15 (1.7)
Sex (n=1389)	
Female	473 (34.1)
Male	916 (65.9)
Age category (n=1391)	
0-2 y	23 (1.7)
2-5 y	28 (2.0)
5-15 y	77 (5.5)
16-30 y	273 (19.6)
31-49 y	477 (34.3)
50-65 y	389 (28.0)
>65 y	124 (8.9)
Weight categories (n=914)	
>100 kg	40 (4.4)
<50 kg	109 (11.9)

*> 6 months in the last 12 months

Table 1. Population characteristics of artesunate-treated patients (France, May 2011 – December 2017).

	N (% of available data)
Prescription of artesunate (n=1391)	
1st intention	1135 (81.6)
2nd intention	256 (18.4)
Treatment received before artesunate when given in 2nd intention (n=1388)	
Quinine (IV or PO)	146 (57.7)
Atovaquone + Proguanil	54 (21.3)
Artemether + Lumefantrine	23 (9.1)
Dihydroartemisinin + piperaquine	22 (8.7)
Mefloquine	5 (2.0)
Chloroquine	1 (0.4)
Other	2 (0.8)
Severity (n=1391)	
Uncomplicated malaria without vomiting	13 (0.9)
Uncomplicated malaria with vomiting	8 (0.6)
Severe malaria	1370 (98.5)
Plasmodium species (n=1391)	
<i>P. falciparum</i> alone or co-infection*	1381 (99.3)
Other**	10 (0.7)
Place malaria acquired (n=1344)	
West Africa	800 (59.5)
East and Central Africa	521 (38.8)
South America	5 (0.4)
Asia	6 (0.4)
Other	12 (0.9)
Chemoprophylaxis during travel (n=1247)	
yes	271 (21.7)
Atovaquone+Proguanil	76 (28.0)
Mefloquine	42 (15.5)
Doxycycline	101 (37.3)
Chloroquine	26 (9.6)
Proguanil	15 (5.5)
Other	11 (4.1)
Reason for stay in malaria-endemic zone (n=1037)	
VFR	535 (51.6)
Tourism	78 (7.5)
Tourism from endemic zone	117 (11.3)
Business in endemic zone	140 (13.5)
Expatriate	66 (6.4)
Military	29 (2.8)
Humanitarian	38 (3.7)
Seafarers	5 (0.5)
Other	29 (2.8)
Length of stay (n=1138)	
<4 weeks	403 (35.4)
4-12 weeks	456 (40.1)
>12 weeks	279 (24.5)
Evolution (n=1011)	
Died	41 (4.1)
Sequelae (n=574)	
Sequelae	48 (8.4)

	N (% of available data)
Severity criteria (clinical) (n=1391)	
Impaired consciousness	475 (34.7)
Coma (Glasgow score < 11)	62 (4.5)
Repeated generalized seizures	12 (0.9)
Circulatory collapse	167 (12.2)
Spontaneous bleeding	44 (3.2)
Respiratory distress	70 (5.1)
Macroscopic hemoglobinuria	136 (9.9)
Clinical jaundice	417 (30.4)
Severity criteria (biological) (n=1391)	
Hyperparasitemia > 4%	820 (59.9)
Hemoglobin < 5 g/dL, hematocrit < 15%	12 (0.9)
Hemoglobin < 7g/dL, hematocrit < 20%	54 (3.9)
Creatinine > 265 µmol/L or elevated for age	215 (15.7)
Hypoglycemia (< 2.2 mmol/L)	23 (1.7)
Total bilirubin > 50 µmol/L	446 (32.6)
Hyperlactatemia > 5 mmol/l	404 (29.5)
Acidosis (pH < 7.35 or sodium bicarbonate < 15 mmol/L)	101 (7.4)
Severity criteria specific to imported malaria (n=1391)	145 (10.4%)
Isolated hyperparasitemia (4-10%)	131 (9.4)
Isolated hemoglobinuria	8 (0.6%)
Isolated clinical jaundice	6 (0.4%)

	MED (Q1-Q3)
Initial parasitemia (%) (n=1258)	5.2 (1.5-9.6)
Temperature at day 0 (°C) (n=1217)	39 (38-39.7)
Initial dose of artesunate 1st int (mg) (n=882)	180 (150-200)
Time between onset of symptoms and diagnosis (days) (n=1263)	4 (2-6)
Length of stay in intensive care unit (days) (n=866)	2 (1-4)
Length of stay in hospital (days) (n=901)	6 (4-8)

Table 2. Clinical presentation, treatment characteristics and main outcomes in artesunate-treated patients (France. May 2017-December 2017).

*= *P. ovale* (6), *P. vivax* (10), *P. malariae* (11), *P. spp* (1)

**=*P. ovale* (4), *P. vivax* (2), *P. malariae* (1)

	Number of subjects in each group	Mortality			Total length of stay (days)			ICU length of stay (days)		
		N of deaths / N of patients with reported outcome	Estimated frequencies	Statistical significance	Median	(Q1-Q3)	Statistical significance	Median	(Q1-Q3)	Statistical significance
TOTAL	1391	41/1011	4.1%		6	(4-8)		2	(1-4)	
Geographic origin										
African	829	13/615	2.1%	p<0.000	5	(4-7)	p=0.0001	2	(1-3)	p=0.0001
European	362	20/289	6.9%	p=0.007	7	(5-9)		3	(1.5-4)	
Age										
<2 years	23	0/17	0%	p=0.003	5	(4-6)	p=0.0023	1	(0-3)	p=0.0125
2-5 years	28	1/19	5.3%		4.5	(3.5-6)		3	(1-4)	
6-15 years	77	0/60	0%		5	(4-8)		2	(1-3)	
16-30 years	273	6/194	3.1%		5	(4-7)		2	(1-3)	
31-49 years	477	6/336	1.8%		6	(4-7)		2	(1-3)	
≥50 years	513	28/385	7.3%		6	(4-8)		3	(1-4)	
Pregnancy*	15	0/5	0%	p=1.000	7	(5.5-10)	p=0.2010	2	(1-4)	p=0.8564
Weight categories										
Weight <50 kg	109	2/91	2.2%	p=1.000	6	(4-7.5)	0.1323	2	(1-4)	p=0.0089
Weight 50-100 kg	765	19/590	3.2%		6	(4-8)		2	(1-4)	
Weight >100 kg	40	1/33	3.0%		7	(5-9)		3	(3-5)	
HIV+ [§]	67	1/41	1.8%	p=0.724	7	(5-10)	p=0.0102	2	(1-3)	p=0.7096
Parasitemia										
Parasitemia <4	511	12/394	3.0%	p<0.000	6	(4-8)	p=0.0028	2	(1-3)	p=0.0001
Parasitemia 4-10	466	7/350	2.0%		5	(4-7)		2	(1-3)	
Parasitemia >10	281	19/206	9.2%		7	(4.5-9.5)		3	(2-4)	

Table 3-1. Main outcomes in different subgroups. * comparisons were made versus patients without notified pregnancy. § comparisons were made versus patient without notified HIV-positive status.

	Number of subjects in each group	Number of subjects with available data on AE	Anemia and/or hemolysis			Cardiovascular AEs			Renal failure (%)		
			N	Estimated frequencies	Statistical significance	N	Estimated frequencies	Statistical significance	N	Estimated frequencies	Statistical significance
TOTAL	1391	568	136	23.9%		24	4.2%		15	2.6%	
Geographic origin											
African	829	333	58	17.4%	p<0.000	6	1.8%	p=0.002	6	1.8%	p=0.018
European	362	162	60	37.0%	p<0.000	12	7.4%	p=0.011	10	6.2%	p=0.030
Age											
<2 years	23	8	1	12.5%	p=0.680	0	0.0%	p=0.575	0	0.0%	p=0.946
2-5 years	28	14	1	7.1%		1	7.1%		0	0.0%	
6-15 years	77	39	8	20.5%		2	5.1%		1	2.6%	
16-30 years	273	111	24	21.6%		3	2.7%		4	3.6%	
31-49 years	477	200	51	25.5%		5	2.5%		5	2.5%	
≥50 years	513	196	49	25.0%		9	4.6%		8	4.1%	
Pregnancy*	15	8	3	37.5%	p=0.399	0	0.0%	p=1.000	0	0.0%	p=1.000
Weight categories											
Weight <50 kg	109	54	12	22.2%	p=0.137	3	5.6%	p=0.520	2	3.7%	p=1.000
Weight 50-100 kg	765	365	91	24.9%		13	3.6%		13	3.6%	
Weight >100 kg	40	19	1	5.3%		0	0.0%		0	0.0%	
HIV+ [§]	67	22	4	18.2%	p=0.798	0	0.0%	p=1.000	0	0.0%	p=1.000
Parasitemia											
Parasitemia <4	511	199	28	14.1%	p<0.000	9	4.5%	p=0.807	4	2.0%	p=0.021
Parasitemia 4-10	466	191	45	23.6%		6	3.1%		2	1.0%	
Parasitemia >10	281	129	51	39.5%		5	3.9%		8	6.2%	

*** Table 3-2. Main adverse events in different subgroups.** *comparisons were made versus patients without notified pregnancy. § comparisons were made versus patient without notified HIV-positive status. § according to univariate analysis.

FIGURES

Figure 1. Medical context, kinetics and completeness of artesunate implementation in France (May 2011-December 2017).

A. Annual incidence of malaria (grey bars) and proportion of severe malaria cases (red line). **B.** Lethality of malaria (black line) and specific lethality of severe malaria (red line). **C.** Proportion of patients with severe malaria treated with IV artesunate (red line), IV quinine (blue line) or oral therapy (black line). **D.** Proportion of patients with severe malaria cases treated orally with atovaquone-Proguanil (AP, green line), artemisinin-based combination therapies (ACT, red line) or other drugs (blue line).

Figure 2. Adverse events declared in patients treated with artesunate. MOF= Multiorgan failure, NOS= not otherwise specified, AI= auto-immune, *see Table S3 for further details.

Figure S1. ANSM forms for the temporary use authorization program

ATU nominative
MALACEF® (artésunate) 60mg, poudre et solvant pour solution injectable
Fiche de demande initiale de traitement 1/2

Identification du patient

Nom (3 premières lettres) : Prénom (2 premières lettres) :

Date de Naissance :/...../..... Pays de naissance :

Poids :kg Sexe M F

Pays de contamination :

Date d'arrivée dans ce pays :

Date de retour en France :

Situation clinique

1- Diagnostic de paludisme Température..... °C

Le diagnostic du paludisme à *P. falciparum* est-il formel? oui non

La méthode ayant permis la confirmation du diagnostic : Test de diagnostic rapide (TDR)

(plusieurs choix possibles) Goutte épaisse

Frottis mince

2- Forme grave de paludisme :

Au moins 1 des 13 critères de gravité suivants (signalés en gras) est requis pour l'utilisation du MALACEF®

Critères de gravité (1 seul critère formel suffit)	Détail de l'examen
1 <input type="checkbox"/> Défaillance neurologique <input type="checkbox"/> obnubilation, confusion, somnolence, prostration <input type="checkbox"/> coma avec score de Glasgow < 11	Confusion Oui <input type="checkbox"/> Non <input type="checkbox"/> Non renseigné <input type="checkbox"/> Convulsion Oui <input type="checkbox"/> Non <input type="checkbox"/> Non renseigné <input type="checkbox"/> Nombre depuis 24h :
2 <input type="checkbox"/> Convulsions répétées : au moins 2 par 24 h	Score de Glasgow /15
3 <input type="checkbox"/> Défaillance respiratoire <input type="checkbox"/> PaO ₂ /FiO ₂ < 300 mmHg, si VM ou VNI <input type="checkbox"/> PaO ₂ < 60 mmHg et/ou SpO ₂ < 90 % en air ambiant et/ou FR > 32/mn si non ventilé <input type="checkbox"/> signes radiologiques : images interstitielles et/ou alvéolaires	Saturation :% FR :/mn PaO ₂ :mmHg O ₂ nasal l/mn PCO ₂ :mmHg FiO ₂% Bruits surajoutés à l'auscultation (préciser) :
4 <input type="checkbox"/> Défaillance cardio-circulatoire : <input type="checkbox"/> pression artérielle systolique <80 mmHg en présence de signes périphériques d'insuffisance circulatoire <input type="checkbox"/> patient recevant des drogues vasoactives quel que soit le chiffre de pression artérielle <input type="checkbox"/> signes périphériques d'insuffisance circulatoire sans hypotension	TA :/..... Pouls :/mn Drogues vasopressives Oui <input type="checkbox"/> Non <input type="checkbox"/> Non renseigné <input type="checkbox"/>
5 <input type="checkbox"/> Hémorragie : définition clinique	Saignement spontané Oui <input type="checkbox"/> Non <input type="checkbox"/> Non renseigné <input type="checkbox"/> Purpura Oui <input type="checkbox"/> Non <input type="checkbox"/> Non renseigné <input type="checkbox"/>
6 <input type="checkbox"/> Ictère : clinique ou bilirubine totale > 50 µmol/l	Ictère clinique Oui <input type="checkbox"/> Non <input type="checkbox"/> Non renseigné <input type="checkbox"/> Splénomégalie Oui <input type="checkbox"/> Non <input type="checkbox"/> Non renseigné <input type="checkbox"/> Splénectomie Oui <input type="checkbox"/> Non <input type="checkbox"/> Non renseigné <input type="checkbox"/> Bilirubine T (micromol/l) : PA :GGT..... AST/ALT (UI/l) :/.....
7 <input type="checkbox"/> Anémie profonde : hémoglobine < 7 g/dl, hématocrite < 20%	Ht (%) : Taux d'Hb (g/dl): Plaquettes :giga/l GB..... giga/l
8 <input type="checkbox"/> Hypoglycémie : glycémie < 2,2 mmol/l	Glycémie (avant traitement) (g/l ou mmol/l)
9 <input type="checkbox"/> Acidose : <input type="checkbox"/> bicarbonates plasmatiques <15 mmol/l <input type="checkbox"/> acidémie avec PH < 7,35	pH : HC03- :mmol/l Diurèse (ml/24h) :
10 <input type="checkbox"/> Insuffisance rénale : <input type="checkbox"/> créatininémie > 265 µmol/l ou urée sanguine > 17 mmol/l <input type="checkbox"/> diurèse < 400 ml/24 h malgré réhydratation	Créatininémie (micromol/l) : Urée sanguine (mmol/l) :
11 <input type="checkbox"/> Toute hyperlactatémie	Lactates (mmo/l) :
12 <input type="checkbox"/> Hyperparasitémie : > 4% (Adulte) > 10% (Enfant)	Parasitémie %d'hématies parasitées

VM : ventilation mécanique ; VNI : ventilation non invasive ; FR : fréquence respiratoire

ATU nominative
MALACEF® (artésunate) 60mg, poudre et solvant pour solution injectable
Fiche de demande initiale de traitement **2/2**

Nom (3 premières lettres) : **Prénom (2 premières lettres) :**

Traitements antérieurs

Date des premiers symptômes :/...../.....

- ◆ Chimio prophylaxie utilisée : OUI NON NSP
Si oui, laquelle : atovaquone proguanil (MALARONE®)
 doxycycline (DOXYPALU®, ou autre)
 méfloquine (LARIAM®)
 chloroquine proguanil (SAVARINE®)
 autre (à préciser) :

◆ Traitement curatif initié depuis moins d'1 mois : OUI NON NSP
Si oui, lequel :

◆ Traitement en cours lors de l'admission OUI NON NSP
Si oui, lequel :
Posologie.....Date et heure de début.....

Si le patient reçoit de la quinine depuis moins de 24 heures, un relai par MALACEF® est possible

Traitement par MALACEF®

- Posologie envisagée :**
 2,4 mg/kg H0, H12, H24, H48, H72
 3 mg/kg H0, H12, H24, H48, H72 (enfant < 20 kg)

Je soussigné Dr _____ m'engage à fournir à l'ANSM et au CNR du paludisme de la Pitié Salpêtrière la fiche de fin de traitement ainsi que la fiche de suivi post-traitement dès que possible.

Nom de l'établissement :	
Médecin prescripteur	Pharmacien
Nom :	Nom :
Service :	Nombre de flacons délivrés :
.....	Date/heure :
Tél :	
mail :	Date et signature:
Date et signature	

Merci de bien vouloir adresser la fiche de demande initiale avec le formulaire Cerfa de demande d'ATU nominative au pharmacien de l'établissement qui se chargera de l'envoyer par fax à :

Agence nationale de sécurité du médicament et des produits de santé
Direction des médicaments anti-infectieux
143, 147 boulevard Anatole France
93285 Saint Denis Cedex
Fax : 01.55.87.34.02 Tél. : 01.55.87.36.24

Une copie de cette fiche doit également être adressée au Centre de Référence du Paludisme (site Hôpital Pitié Salpêtrière) dans les meilleurs délais par fax au 01 42 16 13 28

ATU nominative
MALACEF® (artésunate) 60mg, poudre et solvant pour solution injectable
Fiche de fin de traitement 1/2

Identification du patient

Nom (3 premières lettres) : Prénom (2 premières lettres) : ATU N°

Date de Naissance :/...../..... Poids :kg Sexe M F

Date de la consultation de suivi :/...../.....

Traitement par MALACEF®

Date du diagnostic :/...../.....

Date de début de traitement :/...../..... Posologie :

Date de fin de traitement :/...../....., si arrêt prématuré, motif :

Nombre de doses de MALACEF® reçues au total :

Évolution sous traitement par MALACEF®

◆ Résultat de la recherche de *Plasmodium falciparum* à la fin du traitement par MALACEF® :

date :/...../..... : négatif positif, préciser la valeur de la parasitémie :

◆ Complications du paludisme après le début du traitement par MALACEF® : (Cocher tous les choix qui s'appliquent et préciser la date de survenue)

	date
<input type="checkbox"/> Troubles de la conscience ou coma avec Score de Glasgow :	
<input type="checkbox"/> Prostration	
<input type="checkbox"/> Convulsions généralisées répétées (plus de 2 crises/24heures)	
<input type="checkbox"/> Défaillance respiratoire ou Œdème pulmonaire (radiologique)	
<input type="checkbox"/> Ictère clinique ou taux de bilirubine totale > 50 :mol/l	
<input type="checkbox"/> Hémorragie clinique ou hémoglobinurie macroscopique	
<input type="checkbox"/> Défaillance cardio-circulatoire	
<input type="checkbox"/> Insuffisance rénale (créatinémie > 265µmol/l et diurèse < 400 ml/24h),	
<input type="checkbox"/> Acidose (HCO3 plasmatique < 15 mmol/l ou pH < 7,35)	
<input type="checkbox"/> Hyperlactatémie	
<input type="checkbox"/> Hypoglycémie (<2.2 mmol/l ou < 40 mg/dl),	
<input type="checkbox"/> Anémie grave (Hb < 7 g/dl, hématocrite < 20%)	
<input type="checkbox"/> Autre :	

◆ Présence de complications résiduelles au jour 7? Oui Non

Si oui, préciser :

◆ Survenue d'effet(s) indésirable(s) lié(s) au MALACEF®? OUI* NON

Si oui, préciser :

.....

(*Remplir également la fiche de déclaration d'effet indésirable)

Text S1. Severe malaria criteria for adults and children used for the study

Severe malaria criteria according to the 2007 French definition for adults (SPILF, Recommendations for clinical practice. Management and prevention of imported Plasmodium falciparum malaria. Revision 2007 of the 1999 Consensus conference. Short text. Med Mal Infect, 2008. 38(2): p. 54-67, 39-53.)

1. Cerebral malaria including impaired consciousness or unarousable coma with a Glasgow coma score of 11 or less
2. Pulmonary edema with the presence of criteria for acute respiratory distress syndrome or acute lung injury
3. Circulatory collapse with systolic blood pressure < 80 mmHg
4. Repeated generalized seizures 2/24 hours
5. Spontaneous bleeding
6. Clinical jaundice or total bilirubin level > 50 micromole/L
7. Macroscopic hemoglobinuria if definitively related to acute malaria
8. Anemia with a hemoglobin level < 7 g/L for adults, hematocrit level < 20%
9. Hypoglycemia with blood glucose level < 2.2 mmol/L
10. Acidosis (pH < 7.35) or acidosis (serum bicarbonate < 15 mmol/L)
11. Hyperparasitemia > 4%
12. Hyperlactatemia > 5 mmol/L
13. Renal failure with serum creatinine > 265 micromole/L or urea level > 20 mmol/L

Severe malaria criteria according to the 2007 French definition for children (SPILF, Recommendations for clinical practice. Management and prevention of imported Plasmodium falciparum malaria. Revision 2007 of the 1999 Consensus conference. Short text. Med Mal Infect, 2008. 38(2): p. 54-67, 39-53.)

1. Coma with Glasgow coma score of 11 or less
2. Impaired consciousness (GCS between 11 and 15)
3. Repeated generalized seizures > 1/24 hours
4. Prostration
5. Respiratory distress: nasal flaring, Kussmaul dyspnea
6. Clinical jaundice
7. Circulatory collapse with systolic blood pressure < 60 mmHg if less than 5 years old, or < 80 mmHg if more than 5 years old
8. Abnormal bleeding
9. Pulmonary edema (clinical and radiological)
10. Macroscopic hemoglobinuria
11. Hypoglycemia with blood glucose level < 2.2 mmol/L
12. Acidosis (pH < 7.35) or acidosis (serum bicarbonate < 15 mmol/L)
13. Anemia with a hemoglobin level < 5 g/L, hematocrit level < 15%
14. Hyperlactatemia > 5 mmol/L
15. Hyperparasitemia > 4%
16. Renal failure with serum creatinine elevated for age or diuresis < 12 mL/kg/24h

Text S2. Material and Methods.

Case definition

Severe malaria was defined by the combination for a blood smear positive for asexual forms of *Plasmodium* sp. parasites and at least 1 criterion of severity according to the definition of severe malaria used in France since 2007, adapted from WHO criteria. Uncomplicated malaria was defined by a blood smear positive for asexual forms of *Plasmodium* sp. parasites with no severity criterion reported.

Parasitological failure was defined as (i) slow parasitological clearance (presence of trophozoites on blood smear at day 3 and between day 7 and day 28 after treatment initiation) or (ii) early resurgence (blood smear negative at day 3 and trophozoites present at day 7 after treatment initiation) or late resurgence (thin smear negative at day 3 and trophozoites present anytime between day 8 and day 28 after treatment initiation, without visit to an endemic area).

AE consisting of anemia and/or hemolysis were described by clinicians, biologists and pharmacists responsible for patients and/or by pharmacovigilance experts with heterogeneous terminology. Anemia and/or hemolysis recorded as AE in the database were classified by the expert group at the time of the analysis as “not otherwise specified” (NOS), “PADH/late hemolytic anemia”, “persistent hemolytic anemia”, “early anemia and/or hemolysis”, “auto-immune hemolytic anemia” (positive direct antiglobulin test), “anemia other” or “blackwater fever” according to available information and published definitions.⁹

Four categories were used for the variable “geographic origin” : 1. Patients of African origin defined as Black Africa if at least one of the parents was African; 2. Patients of European origin as white European people; 3. Patients of Asian origin as people from the Asian continent (Asian countries were listed at https://www.loc.gov/rr/frd/cs/continent_asia.html); Patients of others origins were those different from the 3 previous categories.

Treatment regimens. Recommended artesunate regimen was 2.4 mg/kg/dose (or 3 mg/kg in children <20kg) at H0, H12, H24, and as long as oral route was not possible. To prevent recrudescence, a switch to oral therapy by an ACT (artemether-lumefantrine or DHA-piperquine) for 3 days was recommended after completion of at least 24 h of artesunate. Regimens of other antimalarials were left at the discretion of the attending physician. Usual IV quinine regimen was 8mg/kg/dose every 8h.

Post-artesunate delayed hemolysis classification

PADH was defined by a decrease in the hemoglobin level and the appearance of hemolytic markers (>10% drop in hemoglobin or >10% rise in LDH levels) occurring after day 8 of treatment initiation. No PADH was defined by a hemoglobin nadir and a hemolysis peak occurring before day 8 of treatment initiation. The indeterminate pattern was defined as all other cases of anemia for which information was lacking and did not allow the allocation to PADH or No PADH groups. Allocation to the PADH, No PADH or indeterminate groups was determined blindly by two experts using previously-published case definitions.

Method for detection of Kelch 13-propeller domain mutations

The genotyping-based detection of artemisinin resistance-associated mutations was accomplished by amplifying the Kelch 13 (K13) protein propeller domain of *P. falciparum* (codons 443–666, i.e. 720 bp) with a nested PCR as per the operating procedure on the WWARN website (<https://www.wwarn.org/tools-resources/procedures/pcr-and-sequencing-genotyping-candidate-plasmodium-falciparum-artemisinin>) Sanger sequencing of PCR products was performed on a 3500 Dx genetic analyzer (Life Technologies) then the sequences were analyzed with SeqScape software (Life Technologies) using PF3D7_1343700 as the reference sequence. Isolates with mixed alleles were considered as mutants. The positive control was the F32-ART strain with the M476I mutation, and the negative control was the ART-sensitive F32-Tanzania strain.

Ethical considerations

As per French law on common public-health missions of all French National Reference Centers (<https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/eli/decret/2016/6/16/AFSP1614128D/jo/texte/fr>), no specific patient consent was required. The analysis of biological samples obtained in the medical care context was considered as non-interventional research (article L1221-1.1 of the French Public Health Code), requiring only the non-opposition of the patient during sampling (article L1211-2 of the French Public Health Code). All collected data were anonymized before analysis.

Table S1. Population characteristics, clinical presentation, treatment characteristics and main outcomes in the PADH-incidence subgroups of 98 patients

	N (% of available data)
Geographic origin (n=97)	
African	62 (63.9)
European	35 (36.1)
Asian	0
Other	0
Location of birth (n=94)	
Endemic area	50 (53.2)
Non-endemic area	44 (46.8)
Location of residence* (n=89)	
Endemic area	12 (13.5)
Non-endemic area	77 (86.5)
Immunodepression (n=92)	
Yes	9 (9.8)
HIV	5 (5.4)
Cancer	0 (0.0)
Corticosteroid therapy	1 (1.1)
Hematological malignancy	1 (1.1)
Organ transplant	0 (0.0)
Other	0 (0.0)
Unknown	2 (2.8)
Pregnancy (n=95)	
Yes	3 (3.2)
Sex (n=98)	
Female	48 (49.0)
Male	50 (51.0)
Age category (n=98)	
0-2 y	1 (1.0)
2-5 y	3 (3.1)
6-15 y	3 (3.1)
16-30 y	18 (18.4)
31-49 y	41 (41.8)
50-65 y	24 (24.5)
>65 y	8 (8.2)
Weight categories (n=81)	
>100	2 (2.5)
<50	8 (9.9)
MED (Q1-Q3)	
Age (years)	42.5 (30.5-51)
Weight (kg)	71 (62.5-81)

	N (% of available data)
Prescription of artesunate (n=98)	
1st intention	84 (85.7)
2nd intention	14 (14.3)
Treatment received before artesunate when given in 2nd intention (n=14)	
Quinine (IV or PO)	6 (42.8)
Atovaquone + Proguanil	3 (21.4)
Artemether + Lumefantrine	3 (21.4)
Dihydroartemisinin + piperazine	0 (0.0)
Mefloquine	2 (14.9)
Chloroquine	0 (0.0)
Other	0 (0.0)
Severity (n=98)	
Simple malaria w/o vomiting	0 (0.0)
Simple malaria w vomiting	0 (0.0)
Severe malaria	98 (100)
Plasmodium species (n=98)	
P. falciparum alone or co-infection*	98 (100)
Other**	0 (0.0)
Place malaria acquired (n=98)	
West Africa	82 (83.7)
East and Central Africa	16 (16.3)
South America	0 (0.0)
Asia	0 (0.0)
Other	0 (0.0)
Chemoprophylaxis during travel (n=95)	
yes	20 (21.0)
Atovaquone + Proguanil	7 (33.3)
Mefloquine	5 (23.8)
Doxycycline	2 (9.5)
Chloroquine	0 (0.0)
Chloroquine-Proguanil	1 (1.0)
Other	5 (23.8)
Reason for stay in malaria-endemic zone (n=91)	
VFR	55 (60.4)
Tourism	9 (9.9)
Tourism to endemic zone	6 (6.6)
business in endemic zone	12 (13.2)
Expatriate	4 (4.4)
Military	0 (0.0)
Humanitarian	3 (3.3)
Seafarers	0 (0.0)
Other	9 (9.9)
Length of stay (n=69)	
<4 weeks	28 (40.6)
4-12 weeks	28 (40.6)
>12 weeks	13 (18.8)
Evolution (n=91)	
Death	0 (0.0)
Sequelae (n=61)	
Sequelae	5 (8.2)

	N (% of available data)
Severity criteria (clinical)(n=98)	
Impaired consciousness	39 (39.8)
Coma (Glasgow score < 11)	4 (4.1)
Repeated generalized seizures	2 (2.0)
Circulatory collapse	19 (19.4)
Spontaneous bleeding	2 (2.0)
Respiratory distress	4 (4.1)
Macroscopic hemoglobinuria	9 (9.2)
Clinical jaundice	32 (32.6)
Severity criteria (biological) (n=98)	
Hyperparasitemia>4%	69 (70.4)
Hemoglobin < 5 g/dL, hematocrit < 15%	1 (1.0)
Hemoglobin < 7g/dL, hematocrit < 20%	6 (6.1)
Creatinine > 265 µmol/L or elevated for age	15 (15.3)
Hypoglycemia (< 2.2 mmol/L)	0 (0.0)
Total bilirubin > 50 µmol/L	33 (33.7)
Hyperlactatemia > 5 mmol/l	39 (39.8)
Acidosis (pH < 7.35 or sodium bicarbonate < 15 mmol/L)	7 (7.1)

	MED (Q1-Q3)
Initial parasitemia (%) (n=98)	6.8 (1.8-10.4)
Temperature at day 0 (°C) (n=97)	39 (38-39.7)
Initial dose of artesunate 1st int (mg) (n=70)	202.5 (150-192)
Time between onset of symptoms and diagnosis (days) (n=95)	4 (3-6)
Length of stay in intensive care unit (days) (n=79)	3 (1-3.2)
Length of stay in hospital (days) (n=81)	6 (5-9)

Table S2. Demographics and clinical characteristics of patients with parasitological failure and controls.

	Parasitological failure	Controls	P value
N	27	291	
Age (years). median (Q1-Q3)	50 (37-58)	43 (30-55)	0.14
Males (%)	70	60.4	0.31
Prolonged exposure to Plasmodium (%)*	14 (53.8%) [‡]	186 (68.6%)**	0.15
Chemoprophylaxis (%)	5 (19.2%) [‡]	68 (24.1%) [§]	0.57
Initial parasitemia (%). median (Q1-Q3)	7.2 (4.2-10.8)	5 (1.7-10)	0.18
Artesunate first line (%)	20(74%)	243 (83.5%)	0.22

* born in endemic area or residency >6 months per year in endemic area or previous malaria infection
 Missing information for [‡] 1 patient. **17 patients. [§]9 patients

Figure S2

The single patient who died after day 28 (day 40) was not included in this representation

Table S3. Initial parasitemia in patient subgroups

	Number of subjects in each group	Initial parasitemia		
		Median	(Q1-Q3)	Statistical significance
TOTAL	1391	5.2	(1.5-9.6)	
Geographic origin				
African	829	4.5	(1.3-8)	p=0.0001
European	362	7	(2.9-13)	
Age				
<2 years	23	7.1	(4.3-12)	p=0.195
2-5 years	28	6.5	(3-12.8)	
6-15 years	77	4.5	(1.4-7.6)	
16-30 years	273	5	(2-8.5)	
31-49 years	477	5.05	(1.3-10)	
≥50 years	513	5.35	(1.5-10.5)	
Pregnancy*	15	3.5	(2-6)	p=0.4231
Weight categories				
Weight <50 kg	109	6.5	(2.4-10)	p=0.2304
Weight 50-100 kg	765	5.15	(1.5-10)	
Weight >100 kg	40	3.6	(1-9)	
HIV+	67	4.6	(1.05-8.55)	p=0.5211
Parasitemia				
Parasitemia <4	511	1	(0.4-2.2)	-
Parasitemia 4-10	466	6.8	(5.1-8)	
Parasitemia >10	281	17	(13-25)	

Table S4. Sequelae declared at day 28 (n=60), in 48 patients. MCA= middle central artery

Renal	22
Kidney failure	22
Neurological	20
NOS	4
Asthenia	2
Headaches	2
Memory loss	1
Motor deficit	3
Cognitive impairment	1
Psychomotor slowing	1
Behavioral disorders	2
Uncertain MCA stroke	1
PMNS (post malaria neurological syndrome)	1
Seizures	1
Speech disorders	1
Hepato-splenic and pancreatic	7
Elevation of liver enzymes*	4
Splenectomy	2
Acute pancreatitis	1
Cardiovascular	5
Necrosis of the extremities and amputation	5
Hematological	4
Persistent anemia	4
Ear Nose & Throat	1
Macroglossia due to traumatic intubation	1
NOS	1
TOTAL	60

*Above normal values defined by the laboratory

Table S5. Adverse events

Anemia and / or hemolysis	136	Cardiac arrest	2
Anemia and / or hemolysis NOS	65	Cardiocirculatory NOS	1
PADH/late hemolytic anemia	32	Heart failure	1
Persistent hemolytic anemia	21	hypertensive retinopathy	1
Early anemia and / or hemolysis	9	Repolarization abnormalities	1
Auto-immune hemolytic anemia	5	severe arterial ischemia	1
Anemia other	3	Tachycardia	1
Blackwater fever	1	Ventricular fibrillation	1
Digestive	56	Hematologic (excluding anemia and / or hemolysis)	20
Nausea, Vomiting	19	Thrombocytopenia	5
Cytolytic hepatitis	15	Disseminated intravascular coagulation	5
Intestinal NOS	6	hematologic NOS	3
Cholestatic and cytolytic hepatitis	5	Agranulocytosis	2
Digestive bleeding	3	hemoglobinuria	2
Hepato-bilio-pancreatic NOS	2	Reticulocytopenia	1
Cholestatic hepatitis	2	Neutropenia	1
Elevation of GGT	1	Erythroblastopenia	1
lithiasic cholecystitis	1	Renal	18
Abdominal pain	1	Kidney failure	15
Digestive disorders	1	Renal NOS	3
Neuro-psyhic and sensory	40	Metabolic	16
Altered consciousness, coma	9	Hypoglycemia	5
Cephalalgia	3	Metabolic NOS	3
Hypoacusia	3	Fever	2
Tinnitus	3	Rhabdomyolysis	2
Neuro-psyhic and sensory NOS	2	Hyperlactatemia	2
Dizziness	2	Hyperkaliemia	1
Dysgueusia	2	Hyperglycemia	1
Tremor	1	Cutaneous	14
Otalgia	1	Non-febrile rash	6
Urinary incontinence	1	Cutaneous NOS	3
Aphasia	1	Pruritus	2
Temporospatial disorientation	1	Telogen effluvium	1
cerebellar syndrome	1	Toxiderma	1
Seizures	1	Urticaria	1
diffuse leukoencephalopathy	1	Not otherwise specified (NOS)	13
CNS bleeding	1	Pulmonary	9
CNS ischemia	1	Pulmonary NOS	2
Guillain-Barré syndrome	1	Respiratory failure	2
Gait disturbance	1	Dyspnea	1
Insomnia	1	Severe respiratory distress syndrome	1
Agitation	1	Pulmonary edema	1
Intracranial hypertension	1	Pneumopathy with pleural effusion	1
Facial myoclonus	1	Polypnea	1
Cardiocirculatory	24	Death	9
QT lengthening	6	Multi-organ failure	4
Bradycardia	4	Obstetrical	1
Conduction abnormalities (except QT lengthening)	3	Early spontaneous miscarriage	1
Arrhythmias (except tachy and bradycardia)	1		

Table S6. Cardiocirculatory adverse events

Adverse event	Gender	Age	History of cardiovascular disease	Cardiovascular symptoms before Artesunate	Quinine administration before or after artesunate	Outcome
Severe arterial ischemia	F	44	No	No	Yes	Sequelae : fingers/toes amputation
Hypertensive retinopathy	F	29	No	No	Yes	Cured
Heart failure leading to death in a context of malaria relapse	M	3	Congenital cardiomyopathy	Shock	No	Death (heart failure)
Bradycardia	F	52	No	Shock	No	Cured
Bradycardia	F	13	No	No	No	Cured
QT lengthening (460ms) 5h after the 5th injection of artesunate. Switch for oral AL, QT 560ms 8h after the first intake of AL. Resolution after switch to AP	F	15	No	No	No	Neurological sequelae : hallucinations
QT lengthening 460ms after the 3rd injection of AS	M	40	No	No	No	Cured
5 resuscitated cardiac arrests after the 3rd injection of artesunate in a context of multiorgan failure	M	62	High blood pressure	No	No	Death (day 2)
NOS	M	71	No	Shock	Yes	Death (multi-organ failure)
QT lengthening (500ms) after 6 injection of AS and 1 intake of DHA-P	M	20	No	Shock	Yes	Cured
QT lengthening 3 days after the last injection of AS	M	41	No	Shock	Yes	Sequelae: renal deficiency, anemia
QT lengthening (480ms) after the 4th injection of AS	M	63	High blood pressure, atrial fibrillation	Shock	No	Cured
Tachycardia 4 days after the beginning of AS in a context of septic shock	M	63	High blood pressure	No	No	Death
Ventricular fibrillation 4 days after the beginning of AS in a context of septic Shock						
Bradycardia after the 5th injection of AS	M	20	No	Shock	No	Cured
Conduction abnormalities						
Resuscitated cardiac arrest						
Conduction abnormality (PR lengthening)	M	57	NA	No	Yes	Cured
QT lengthening (480ms) after switch for oral quinine	F	50	Chronic heart failure	Acute heart failure	Yes	Cured
Bradycardia (48bpm) after the 3rd injection of AS	M	48	No	No	No	Cured
Conduction abnormalities after the 3rd injection of AS						
Tachycardia in a context of anemia	M	59	High blood pressure, coronary bypass	No	No	NA
QT lengthening	M	45	NA	No	Yes	Cured
Arrhythmia after the 4th injection of AS	M	70	High blood pressure	No	No	Cured

AL= artemether-lumefantrine, AP= Atovaquone-Proguanil, AS= artesunate, bpm= beat per minute DHA-P= Dihydroartemisine-piperaquine IV= Intravenous, NA= non available

Figure S3. Geographic origin correlates with PADH. Proportion of patient with PADH in groups of African or European origin (p value calculated with Fisher's exact test)

Table S7. Incidence of hypoglycemia and elevation of liver enzymes in patient subgroups.

	Number of subject in each groups	Number of subject with available data on AE	Hypoglycemia (%)			Elevation of liver enzymes		
			N	Estimated frequencies	Statistical significance	N	Estimated frequencies	Statistical significance
TOTAL	1391	568	5	0.9%		26	4.6%	
Geographic origin								
African	829	333	3	0.9%	p=1.000	14	4.2%	p=0.394
European	362	162	2	1.2%	p=0.651	10	6.2%	p=0.379
Age								
<2 years	23	8	1	12.5%	p=0.170	0	0.0%	p=0.561
2-5 years	28	14	0	0.0%				
6-15 years	77	39	0	0.0%				
16-30 years	273	111	0	0.0%				
31-49 years	477	200	2	1.0%				
≥50 years	513	196	2	1.0%				
Pregnancy	15	8	1	12.5%	p=0.073	0	0.0%	p=1.000
Weight categories								
Weight<50 kg	109	54	1	1.9%	p=0.068	1	1.9%	p=0.625
Weight 50-100 kg	765	365	2	0.6%				
Weight>100 kg	40	19	1	5.3%				
HIV+	67	22	0	0.0%	p=1.000	0	0.0%	p=0.616
Parasitemia								
Parasitemia<4	511	199	1	0.5%	p=0.549	9	4.5%	p=0.933
Parasitemia 4-10	466	191	3	1.6%				
Parasitemia>10	281	129	1	0.8%				

Text S3. MNRC corresponding sites

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de Rennes), Y. Le Tulzo (Hôpital Pontchaillou de Rennes), C. Perrone (Hôpital Raymond-Poincaré [Garches]), V. Maxime (Hôpital Raymond-Poincaré Garches), M. Thibault (Hôpital René Dubos de Pontoise), E. Devaud (Hôpital René Dubos de Pontoise), S. Mortaza (Hôpital René Dubos de Pontoise), A. Faye (Hôpital Robert Debré de Paris), C. Madre (Hôpital Robert Debré de Paris), J. Naudin (Hôpital Robert Debré de Paris), J.Y. Siriez (Hôpital Robert Debré de Paris), L. Pull (Hôpital Robert Debré de Paris), O. Fenneteau (Hôpital Robert Debré de Paris), P. Sachs (Hôpital Robert Debré de Paris), R. Blonde (Hôpital Robert Debré de Paris), G. Belkadi (Hôpital Saint-Antoine de Paris), P. Roux (Hôpital Saint-Antoine de Paris), O. Bandin (Hôpital Saint-Camille/Bry-sur-Marne), C. Sarfati (Hôpital Saint-Louis de Paris), E. Azoulay (Hôpital Saint-Louis de Paris), F. Derouin (Hôpital Saint-Louis de Paris), F. Taieb (Hôpital Saint-Louis de Paris), J.M. Molina (Hôpital Saint-Louis de Paris), M. De Chambrun (Hôpital Saint-Louis de Paris), P. Houze (Hôpital Saint-Louis de Paris), S. Bretagne (Hôpital Saint-Louis de Paris), S. Gallien (Hôpital Saint-Louis de Paris), S. Hamane (Hôpital Saint-Louis de Paris), V. Lemiale (Hôpital Saint-Louis de Paris), R.O. Calin (Hôpital Tenon de Paris), A. Parrot (Hôpital Tenon de Paris), G. Le Loup (Hôpital Tenon de Paris), G. Pialoux (Hôpital Tenon de Paris), M. Develoux (Hôpital Tenon de Paris), P. Ray (Hôpital Tenon de Paris), S. Dautheville (Hôpital Tenon de Paris), C. Arriuberge (Hôpital Trousseau de Paris), E. Grimprel (Hôpital Trousseau de Paris), B. Quinet (Hôpital Trousseau de Paris), C. Nguyen (Hôpital Trousseau de Paris), D. Popjora (Hôpital Trousseau de Paris), H. Lapillonne (Hôpital Trousseau de Paris), M. Mimoun-Ayache (Hôpital Trousseau de Paris), N. Desuremain (Hôpital Trousseau de Paris), P. Mornand (Hôpital Trousseau de Paris), S. Lasserre (Hôpital Trousseau de Paris), I. Mazurier (Hôpitaux Civils de Colmar), P. Moskovtchenko (Hôpitaux Civils de Colmar), A. Bouaziz (Hospices Civils de Lyon), A. Stoian (Hospices Civils de Lyon), C. Bouisse (Hospices Civils de Lyon), C. Chidiac (Hospices Civils de Lyon), C. Ramade (Hospices Civils de Lyon), F. Peyron (Hospices Civils de Lyon), J. Karsenti (Hospices Civils de Lyon), S. Picot (Hospices Civils de Lyon), B. Pradine (IMTSSA), D. Parzy (IMTSSA), M. Madamet (IMTSSA), M.P. Carlotti (IMTSSA), A. Durand (Institut Pasteur, Paris), A.S. Le Guern (Institut Pasteur, Paris), P.H. Consigny (Institut Pasteur, Paris), A. Taieb (INTS, Paris), A. Ndour (INTS, Paris), B. Henry (INTS, Paris), C. Chambrion (INTS, Paris), C. Roussel (INTS, Paris), P. Buffet (INTS, Paris)